

DAS RESEARCH SQUIRREL ENGINEERS NETWORK

DIGITALE SERVICES ZUM DIGITALEN DATENMANAGEMENT

AUS DER ARCHÄOINFORMATIK- UND CITIZEN SCIENCE-COMMUNITY

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SQUIRREL PAPERS

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FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

DIE NACHVOLLZIEHBARE FAIRIFIZIERUNG VON FORSCHUNGSDATEN
WIRD IN DER CITIZEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY IMMER WICHTIGER ...

... UM EIN TEIL DES WISSENSGRAPHEN ZU WERDEN
UND IHN DURCH QUALIFIZIERTE DATEN ANZUREICHERN.

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

SO KÖNNEN DIESE DATEN VERKNÜPFT WERDEN UND IN INTERNATIONALE
INITIATIVEN UND COMMUNITY-HUBS AKTIV EINGEBUNDEN WERDEN.

DABEI SIND OPEN SOURCE (FLOSS) RESEARCH UND FAIRIFICATION TOOLS LEIDER OFT NICHT VERFÜGBAR.

DIESE KÖNNEN VON COMMUNITY- UND FREIWILLIGEN-INITIATIVEN WIE
Z.B. DEM RESEARCH SQUIRREL ENGINEERS NETWORK
JEDOCH ERSTELLT UND KURATIERT WERDEN.

DAS RESEARCH SQUIRREL ENGINEERS NETWORK IST EIN LOSER ZUSAMMENSCHLUSS VON LINKED OPEN DATA/WIKIDATA-ENTHUSIAS*INNEN, RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEERS UND CITIZEN SCIENTISTS MIT DEN SCHWERPUNKTEN ARCHÄOINFORMATIK, DIGITAL HUMANITIES UND GEOINFORMATIK.

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DIE MITGLIEDER ENTWICKELN UND MAINTAINEN ZUSAMMEN RESEARCH UND FAIRIFICATION TOOLS UND SETZEN DIESE IN KONKRETEN PROJEKTEN UM.

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

SPARQL UNICORN

EIN FAIRIFICATION TOOL FÜR DAS DIGITALE DATENMANAGEMENT IST DAS
SPARQL UNICORN UND DESSEN IMPLEMENTIERUNG FÜR QGIS.

Das SPARQL Unicorn ermöglicht es, Linked-Data-Anfragen in (Geo)SPARQL an Triplestores zu senden und bereitet die Ergebnisse für die Geocommunity in QGIS auf.

THE SPARQLING UNICORN QGIS PLUGIN

Das Plugin bietet drei Funktionen:

- (A) Vereinfachte Abfrage von Semantic Web Datenquellen
- (B) Transformation von QGIS-Vektorebenen nach RDF
- (C) RDF HTML-Dokumentation

THE SPARQLING UNICORN'S FUNCTIONS

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

SPARQL UNICORN

- - - - -

VEREINFACHTE ABFRAGE VON SEMANTIC WEB DATENQUELLEN

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Item+Label Layer Name: holy_wells

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q126443332.
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
8 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname:

Layer hinzufügen

<https://w.wiki/BD2C>

Unbenanntes Projekt - QGIS

Projekt Bearbeiten Ansicht Layer Einstellungen Ergänzungen Vektor Editor Datenbank Web Netz Verarbeitung Hilfe

GeoConcepts (500) FeatureCollections GeometryCC

- Antarctic field camp (wd:Q4771007)
- Antarctic research station (wd:Q749622)

Browser

- Google Terrain
- Google Terrain-Hybrid
- Mapbox Global Terrain
- Open Weather Map Clouds
- Open Weather Map Temperature
- Open Weather Map Wind Speed
- OpenStreetMap
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.
- OpenStreetMap Monochrome
- OpenStreetMap Standard
- OpenSpockMap
- Stamen Terrain
- Stamen Toner
- Stamen Toner Light

Layer

- uniconn.holy_wells
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.

Koordinate: 41.6686 70.7856 Maßstab: 1:2527405 Vergrößerung: 200% Drehung: 0.0 ° Zeichen EPSG:3857

WIKIDATA QUERIES IN QGIS - HOLY WELLS

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheffer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: [Nomisma --> ?item ?lat ?lon \[SPARQL Endpoint\]](#) [Quick Add RDF Resource](#) Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 100 Random Places Layer Name: Northamptonshire

Unknown namespace prefix : geo

```

1 PREFIX crm: <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>
2 SELECT ?item ?type ?date ?place ?lat ?lon WHERE {
3 ?item nmo:hasFindspot/crm:P7_took_place_at/crm:P89_falls_within ?place ;
4 nmo:hasTypeSeriesItem ?type ;
5 a nmo:NumismaticObject .
6 ?place crm:P89_falls_within+ <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23115> .
7 ?type nmo:hasEndDate ?date .
8 ?place geo:location ?loc .
9 ?loc geo:lat ?lat ;
10 geo:long ?lon .
11 } ORDER BY ASC(?date)

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for qu

NOMISMA.ORG - ALL COINS FOUND IN NORTHAMPTONSHIRE, ORDERED CHRONOLOGICALLY BY ISSUE

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheffer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Roman Open Data --> ?item ?lat ?lon [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 100 Random Geometries Layer Name: rod_Gauloise4

GeoConcepts (2) FeatureCollections

- ont:Municipality
- ont:Place

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX : <http://www.semanticweb.org/ontologies/2015/1/EPNet-ONTOP_Ontology#>
2 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
4 SELECT ?item ?amphtype ?lat ?lon (count(?item) as ?count)
5 WHERE {
6   ?amph a :Amphora .
7   ?amph :hasAmphoraType ?amphtype .
8   ?amphtype dcterms:title ?amphtype .
9   FILTER (?amphtype = "Gauloise 4")
10  ?amph :carries ?inscription .
11  ?amph :hasFindingPlace ?findplace .
12  ?findplace :fallsWithin ?mun .
13  ?mun a :Municipality .
14  ?mun dcterms:title ?item .
15  ?mun :hasLatitude ?lat .
16  ?mun :hasLongitude ?lon .
17 } ORDER BY ?item DESC(?count)

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

ROMAN OPEN DATA - GAULOISE 4 AMPHORAS

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheifer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Research Squirrel Engineers Triplestore --> ?item ?geo [C] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: HWforts

Filter Concept Results:

GeoConcepts (17) FeatureCollections GeometryCol

- Watchtower
- hw:CoastalSite
- hw:Cumbrian_Coast
- hw:Curtain_wall
- hw:Fort

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?name ?latin_name ?typeLabel WHERE {
2   ?item rdf:type hw:Fort .
3   ?item geosparql:hasGeometry ?item_geom .
4   ?item_geom geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
5   ?item hw:name ?name .
6   ?item hw:latin_name ?latin_name .
7   ?item a ?type .
8   ?type rdfs:label ?typeLabel.
9   FILTER NOT EXISTS {
10    FILTER (?typeLabel = "Fort"@en)
11  }
12 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname:

	id	latin_name	name	typeLabel
1	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#19	Bibra (?)	Beckfoot	Cumbrian Coast
2	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#4	Condercum	Benwell	Hadrian's Wall
3	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#33	Fanum Cocidi (?)	Bewcastle	Outpost Fort
4	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#38	Vinovia	Binchester	Support Fort
5	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#12	Banna	Birdoswald	Stanegate
6	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#36	Blatobulgium	Birrens	Outpost Fort
7	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#18	Maia	Bowness-on-So...	Hadrian's Wall
8	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#14	-	Brampton Old ...	Stanegate
9	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#39	Brocavum	Brougham	Support Fort
10	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#16	Aballava	Burgh-by-Sands	Hadrian's Wall
11	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#20	-	Burrow Walls	Cumbrian Coast
12	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#23	Luguvalium	Cerisla	Stanegate
13	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#7	Brocolitia	Carrawburgh	Hadrian's Wall
14	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#11	Magna	Carvoran	Stanegate
15	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#13	Camboglanna	Castlesteads	Hadrian's Wall
16	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#27	Concangis	Chester-le-Street	Support Fort
17	http://hadrianswall.squirrel.link/fort#8	Cilurnum	Chesters	Hadrian's Wall

SQUIRREL STORE - HADRIAN'S WALL FORTS

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?geo ?itemLabel ?stone ?stoneLabel ?readingLabel WHERE {
2 ?stone oghamonto:shows ogham:OW6.
3 ?stone rdfs:label ?stoneLabel .
4 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
5 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
6 ?item rdfs:label ?itemLabel .
7 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?geom_obj .
8 ?geom_obj geosparql:asWKT ?geo .
9 ?stone oghamonto:carries ?inscription .
10 ?inscription oghamonto:identifiedAs ?reading .
11 ?reading rdfs:label ?readingLabel .
12 FILTER(regex(?readingLabel, "MAQI"))
13 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname:

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (9) FeatureCollections GeometryColl

- Barony
- Barony (oghamonto:Barony)
- County
- County (oghamonto:County)
- Feature (geosparql:Feature)
- Geographic Location ...
- Location
- Ogham Site (oghamonto:OghamSite)
- Pleiades Place (Place)

OGHAM STORE - OGHAM STONES WITH MAQI (SON OF)

SPARQLing Unicorm QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name:

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo WHERE {
2 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <> .
3 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
4 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
5 } LIMIT 10

```


Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

GeometryCollections ClassTree (426)

- taxonomy
- terminology
- thesaurus
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing
- Annotation
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- OghamSite
- OghamStone
- OghamStone_CIIC
- OghamStone_CISP
- OghamStone_O3D
- OghamStone_Squirrel
- Place
 - Place
 - Aufbewahrungsort (Repository)
 - Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
 - Kiln region (KilnRegion)
 - ProductionCentre
 - Location (Location)
 - Townland
 - Townland
 - geosparql:Feature

NFDI4OBJECTS KNOWLEDGE GRAPH

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheifer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: Engl

Filter Concept Results:

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kin region (KinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite**
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- FeatureCollections
- GeometryCollecti...
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: /api/sparql [see documentation]

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Example queries: (Please select)

Table Response 196 results

Item	label	geo	county	count
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000001>	Ballyneek (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.071111 52.026644)"	"Cork"	15
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000002>	Drumshanahilly (Ogham Site)	"POINT(7.648056 52.163056)"	"Waterford"	10
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000003>	Ballinacorney (Ogham Site)	"POINT(10.031111 52.172222)"	"Kerry"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000014>	Killeshane East / Kilmullichah (Ogham Site)	"POINT(9.747222 52.071644)"	"Kerry"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000017>	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	"POINT(7.621111889)"	"Waterford"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000019>	Ballynawing (Ogham Site)	"POINT(10.586111 52.176111)"	"Kerry"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000019>	Colmshagart (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.442778 52.061111)"	"Kerry"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000019>	Cobhstown / Kilsen Corner (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.256889 52.051111)"	"Wicklow"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Ballybank (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.608333 52.836111)"	"Cork"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000011>	Knockshanawee (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.294722 52.866556)"	"Cork"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Whitefield (Ogham Site)	"POINT(6.203056 52.083556)"	"Cork"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000015>	Kilgrawan (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.249722 52.090556)"	"Waterford"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000018>	Monaleggar (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.279444 51.974444)"	"Cork"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Rockfield / Laharan (Ogham Site)	"POINT(9.631667 52.128889)"	"Kerry"	9
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Rooves More (Ogham Site)	"POINT(8.784167 51.886667)"	"Cork"	9

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

N40 KG - OGHAM STONES / SITES / COUNTIES

- Antrim
- Armagh
- Carlow
- Cavan
- Clare
- Cork
- Donegal
- Dublin
- Fermanagh
- Galway
- Kerry
- Kildare
- Kilkenny
- Leitrim
- Limerick
- Londonderry
- Louth
- Mayo
- Meath
- Roscommon
- Tipperary
- Tyrone
- Waterford
- Wexford
- Wicklow

- 1 - 2
- 2 - 3
- 3 - 4
- 4 - 5
- 5 - 6
- 6 - 7
- 7 - 8
- 8 - 9
- 9 - 10
- 10 - 11
- 11 - 12
- 12 - 13
- 13 - 14
- 14 - 15

N40 KG - OGHAM STONES / SITES / COUNTIES

<https://t1p.de/mdvhn>

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFD40Objects Graph -> ?item ?geo [GeosPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: productioncentre

Valid Query

```
1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 SELECT ?item ?geo ?kilnregion WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://archaeology.link/ontology#ProductionCentre .
5 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
6 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
7 ?item lado:clusteredAs ?kr .
8 ?kr rdfs:label ?kilnregion .
9 }
```

GeoConcepts (23) FeatureCollections GeometryCollecti

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kiln region (KilnRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre**
- Province
- State
- Townland
- geosparqlFeature
- sfMultiPolygon
- sfPoint
- sfPolygon
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Layer hinzufügen Query speichern

Language for query results: English (en)

N40 KG - SAMIAN WARE PRODUCTION CENTRES AND KILN REGIONS

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

SPARQL UNICORN

TRANSFORMATION VON QGIS-VEKTOREBENEN NACH RDF

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo
1	Acerra Sink	Cl findspot related from literature	Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.3624 40.9489)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
2	Acqua Fidia	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 40.9285)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
3	Capezzano	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 40.7119)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
4	Casola	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 40.6993)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
5	Castelcivita Cave	Cl findspot related from literature	Fedde et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(15.2092 40.4956)	fsthigh	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
6	Copечchia	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 40.7198)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
7	Cuma	Cl findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
8	Gulf of Naples	Cl findspot related from literature	Arienzo et al., 2009	POINT(14.2559 40.7192)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
9	Lago Patria (Naples)	Cl findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997;Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.0366 40.9260)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
10	Marina di Cassano (Naples)	Cl findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997	POINT(14.3998 40.6385)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
11	Massaquano (Naples)	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
12	Monte Echia (Naples)	Cl findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
13	Lago Grande di Monticchio	Cl findspot related from literature	Narciso, 1996	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
14	Monticchio (Bagni)	Cl findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
15	Monticchio Lakes	Cl findspot related from literature	Brauer et al., 2009	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
16	Murge Plateau	Cl findspot related from literature	Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper

Hinzuzufügende Elemente wählen | cifindspots_part_full

C:\git\workshop-osf24-main\src\cifindspots_part_full.csv

Suche...

Element	Beschreibung
Point (71)	

Alle wählen Alle abwählen

Optionen

- Layer zu einer Gruppe hinzufügen
- System und interne Tabellen anzeigen
- Leere Vektorlayer anzeigen

Layer hinzufügen Abbrechen

QGIS3

Dieser Layer scheint keine Projektionsangaben zu besitzen. Die Projektion dieses Layers wird auf die des Projektes voreingestellt. Sie können es jedoch unten durch auswählen einer anderen Projektion überschreiben.

Vordefiniertes KBS

Filter

Kürzlich benutzte Koordinatenbezugssysteme

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator	EPSG:3857
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

Vordefinierte Koordinatenreferenzsysteme Veraltete KBS verbergen

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
Voirol 1879 (Paris)	EPSG:4821
Wake Island 1952	EPSG:4733
Wallis (MOP 1976) geographi...	IGNF:WALL76G
Wallis (MOP 1978) geographi...	IGNF:WALL78G
WGS 66	EPSG:4760
WGS 72	EPSG:4322
WGS 72BE	EPSG:4324
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

WGS 84

Eigenschaften

- Geographisch (verwendet Längen- und Breitengrad für Koordinaten)
- Dynamisch (hängt von einem Datum ab, das nicht plattenfixiert ist)
- Überirdischer Körper: Earth
- Basierend auf World Geodetic

OK Abbrechen Hilfe

CAMPANIAN IGNYMBRITE FINDSPOT CSV TO RDF

ofindspots_pant_full — Objekte gesamt:71, gefiltert: 71, gewährt: 0

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo	relatedto	relatedtohow	source	sourcetype	spatialtype	methodtype	agent	methoddesc
1	Aceris Sirdik	CI Findspot rela.	Scandone et al., 1999	POINT(14.3624 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fsIsparlyMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsSink	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
2	Acqua Fidia	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6093 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
3	Capizzano	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
4	Casola	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
5	Castelcivita C	CI Findspot rela.	Fedele et al., 20...	POINT(15.2092 ...)	fsIhigh	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsCave	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
6	Copcechia	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
7	Cuma	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al.,	POINT(14.6359 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
8	Gulf of Naples	CI Findspot rela.	Arienzo et al., 2...	POINT(14.2559 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsBight	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
9	Lago Patria (Na...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.0366 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
10	Marina di Cassa...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3998 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsBight	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
11	Massaquano (N...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
12	Monte Echia (N...	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al.,	POINT(14.2479 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsMountain	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
13	Lago Grande di...	CI Findspot rela.	Narcisi, 1996	POINT(15.6057 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsLake	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
14	Monticchio (Ba...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(15.5699 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI Findspot rela.	Bauer et al., 20...	POINT (15.6098...	fsIhigh	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsLake	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
16	Murge Plateau	CI Findspot rela.	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(16.2833 ...)	fsIlow	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsPlateau	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
17	Naples	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996	POINT(14.2680 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
18	Poccapugno	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.6347 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://www.op...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
19	Paglicci Cave	CI Findspot rela.	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(15.1510 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsCave/IsArch...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
20	Pellezzano	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7546 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
21	Penta	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7979 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
22	Phlegraean Fields	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996...	POINT(14.1402 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsSupervolcano	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
23	Ponti Rossi (In...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.2594 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	https://sws.geo...	fsIsparlyMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
24	Pozzuoli Bay	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996	POINT(14.0890 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsBight	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
25	Pucara	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.6459 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://openstree...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
26	Punta Marmorite	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al.,	POINT(14.1689 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	fsIsparlyClose...	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsUnknownCat...	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
27	Sant'Agata de' ...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.7793 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
28	Sant' Angelo a ...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7402 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
29	San Marco	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.381 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...
30	San Nicola La S...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3313 ...)	fsmedium	findspot menti...	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsIPaperDesc	fsIPaper	fsIsInhabitedPlace	fsIGeoreferenc...	http://ocid.org	set a represent...

Alle Objekte anzeigen

CAMPANIAN IGNYMBRITE FINDSPOT CSV TO RDF


```

suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0 a suni:d1f06db3-dd8c-4b96-a360-f28909f76c65 ;
  suni:agent <http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2877-3204> ;
  suni:certainty "fsl:medium"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:certaintyinfo "Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017).""^^xsd:string ;
  suni:desc "CI findspot related from literature"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:label "Urluia (Romania)"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:literature "Fitzsimmons et al., 2014;Fitzsimmons et al., 2013;Obrecht et al., 2017;Pötter et al., 2021"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:methoddesc "set a representative point based on scientific papers using Google Maps"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:methodtype "fsl:Georeferencing"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:relatedto <http://sws.geonames.org/664132;http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654> ;
  suni:relatedtohow "skos:closeMatch"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:source "fsl:PaperDesc"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:sourcetype "fsl:Paper"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:spatialtype "fsl:InhabitedPlace"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:wkt "POINT(27.9021 44.0947)"^^xsd:string ;
  geo:hasGeometry suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom .

```

```

suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom a geo:Point ;
  geo:asWKT "Point (27.90210000000000079 44.09470000000000312)"^^geo:wktLiteral .

```

CAMPANIAN IGNIMBRITE FINDSPOT CSV TO RDF

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

SPARQL UNICORN

RDF HTML-DOCUMENTATION

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8190763](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190763)

This repository hosts a standalone version of the HTML documentation feature included in the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Rather than initiating the documentation generation within the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin, this python script allows the generation of the documentation standalone or as a Github Action.

The standalone script does not rely on QGIS classes and does not provide the full functionality available in the SPARQLUnicorn QGIS Plugin.

Deviations from the SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin are listed as follows:

- Support for less geometry literals: Only WKT and GeoJSON literals are supported for rendering

Usage Example as Github Action

For a usage example please refer to this repository: https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS_testdata

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc>
via 10.5281/zenodo.8190763

HTML-ERSTELLUNG MIT HILFE DES UNICORNS UND GITHUB ACTIONS

Sophie C. Schmidt, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

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“BRANDENBURG 5.000 V. CHR.” (DISS. SOPHIE C. SCHMIDT)

```
bb5kbc:loc_1 rdf:type lado:Location .
bb5kbc:loc_1 rdf:type prov:Entity .
bb5kbc:loc_1 rdf:type fsl:Site .
bb5kbc:loc_1 fsl:siteType fsl:ArchaeologicalSite .
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:hasType lado:ExcavationSite .
bb5kbc:pc_1 lado:hasLocation bb5kbc:loc_1 .
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:hasPlace bb5kbc:pc_1 .
bb5kbc:loc_1 rdfs:label 'Seelow 20'@de.
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:hasFlurname 'nan'@de.
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:hasGemarkung 'Seelow'@de.
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:hasLocationType 'Siedlung'@de.
bb5kbc:loc_1 geosparql:hasGeometry bb5kbc:loc_1_geom .
bb5kbc:loc_1_geom rdf:type sf:Point .
bb5kbc:loc_1_geom geosparql:asWKT "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT (14.3833333255572 52.5452775430815)"^^geosparql:wktLiteral.
```

```
bb5kbc:con_22 rdf:type lado:Context .
bb5kbc:con_22 rdf:type prov:Entity .
bb5kbc:con_22 lado:feature_type 'Oberflächen'@en.
bb5kbc:con_22 lado:locatedWithin bb5kbc:loc_1 .
bb5kbc:loc_1 lado:belongsTo bb5kbc:con_22 .
```

```
bb5kbc:ic_329 rdf:type lado:InformationCarrier .
bb5kbc:ic_329 rdf:type prov:Entity .
bb5kbc:ic_329 lado:potsherd_type 'Wandscherbe'@en.
bb5kbc:ic_329 lado:partOf bb5kbc:con_22 .
bb5kbc:con_22 lado:contains bb5kbc:ic_329 .
```

RDF: LOCATION 1 - CONTEXT 22 - INFORMATION CARRIER 329

via https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/bb-5kbc/Location_collection/index.html

archaeology.link Brandenburg 5000 BC Data | powered by Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA), Department of Scientific IT

Location Instances Collection EM

http://data.archaeology.link/data/bb5kbc/Location_collection

The Location Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Uniconn QGIS Plugin

Search Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) 10

Property	Value
Type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (geo:FeatureCollection) (x)
label (rdfs:label)	Location Instances Collection (deutsch)
member (rdf:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Angermünde 6 (InLoc_28)• Bercholz zu Bercholz-Meyenburg 5 (InLoc_27)• Bercholz zu Bercholz-Meyenburg 6 (InLoc_28)• Bochow 15 (InLoc_18)• Bochow 16 (InLoc_19)• Bochow 2 (InLoc_20)• Bochow 5 (InLoc_21)• Bochow 6 (InLoc_21)• Bochow 6/7 (InLoc_26)• Bochow 7 (InLoc_22)• Bochow 8 (InLoc_23)• Boitzen 2 (InLoc_13)• Brandeburg 8 (InLoc_11)• Cramzow 5 (InLoc_38)• Cramzow 2 (InLoc_14)• Egidorf bei Königs Wusterhausen 2 (InLoc_3)• Eistenerwida 10 (InLoc_12)• Flämsdorf 10 (InLoc_29)• Flämsdorf 6/1 (6) (InLoc_30)• Flämsdorf 4 (InLoc_34)• Gallun 4 (InLoc_4)• Gartz 7 (InLoc_22)• Cramzow 23 (InLoc_53)• Groß Kienitz 7 (InLoc_23)• GutsMuths bei Schönermark 17/18 (17) (InLoc_31)• Herzsprung 7 (InLoc_32)• Hohenbrück 2 (InLoc_39)• Hohenbrück 3 (InLoc_39)• Hohenbrück 10 (InLoc_2)

BRANDENBURG 5.000 V. CHR. SITES ALS HTML SEITE

Seelow 20_{EN}

http://data.archaeology.link/data/bb5kbc/loc_1

The Seelow 20 resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) (x)
belongsTo (lodo:belongsTo)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ con_1 (no:con_1) ■ con_10 (no:con_10) ■ con_11 (no:con_11) ■ con_12 (no:con_12) ■ con_13 (no:con_13) ■ con_14 (no:con_14) ■ con_15 (no:con_15) ■ con_16 (no:con_16) ■ con_17 (no:con_17) ■ con_18 (no:con_18) ■ con_19 (no:con_19) ■ con_2 (no:con_2) ■ con_20 (no:con_20) ■ con_21 (no:con_21) ■ con_22 (no:con_22) ■ con_23 (no:con_23) ■ con_24 (no:con_24) ■ con_25 (no:con_25) ■ con_26 (no:con_26) ■ con_3 (no:con_3) ■ con_4 (no:con_4) ■ con_5 (no:con_5) ■ con_6 (no:con_6) ■ con_7 (no:con_7) ■ con_8 (no:con_8) ■ con_9 (no:con_9)
hasFlurname (lodo:hasFlurname)	nan (rdf:langString) (iso6391:de)
hasGemarkung (lodo:hasGemarkung)	Seelow (rdf:langString) (iso6391:de)
hasLocationType (lodo:hasLocationType)	Siedlung (rdf:langString) (iso6391:de)
hasPlace (lodo:hasPlace)	Seelow 20 (no:pc_1)
hasType (lodo:hasType)	ExcavationSite (lodo:ExcavationSite) (x)
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	loc_1_geom (no:loc_1_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Entity (prov:Entity) (x) ■ Location (lodo:Location) (x) ■ Site (fsl:Site) (x)
label (rdfs:label)	Seelow 20 (rdf:langString) (iso6391:de)
Is hasLocation (lodo:hasLocation) of	Seelow 20 (no:pc_1)
Is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Entity Instances Collection (no:Entity_collection) ■ Location Instances Collection (no:Location_collection) ■ Site Instances Collection (no:Site_collection)

HTML: SITE SEELOW 20 (LOC 1)

con_22_{EN}

http://data.archaeology.link/data/bb5kbc/con_22

The con_22 resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
contains (lado:contains)	ic_329 (no:ic_329)
feature_type (lado:feature_type)	Oberflächen (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
locatedWithin (lado:locatedWithin)	loc_1 (no:loc_1)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Context (lado:Context) [x]Entity (prov:Entity) [x]
Is partOf (lado:partOf) of	ic_329 (no:ic_329)
Is member (rdfs:member) of	Entity Instances Collection (no:Entity_

via https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/bb-5kbc/ic_329/index.html

ic_329_{EN}

http://data.archaeology.link/data/bb5kbc/ic_329

The ic_329 resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
partOf (lado:partOf)	con_22 (no:con_22)
potsherd_type (lado:potsherd_type)	Wandscherbe (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Entity (prov:Entity) [x]InformationCarrier (lado:InformationCarrier) [x]
Is contains (lado:contains) of	con_22 (no:con_22)
Is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Entity Instances Collection (no:Entity_collection)InformationCarrier Instances Collection (no:InformationCarrier_collection)

HTML: CONTEXT 22 / INFORMATION CARRIER 329

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

FUZZY SPATIAL

LOCATIONS ONTOLOGY

FUZZY SPATIAL LOCATIONS ONTOLOGY

FUZZY SPATIAL LOCATIONS ONTOLOGY BASIERT AUF DEM PROV-O MODEL

Breislak, Scipione (1748-1826). Voyages physiques et lythologiques dans la Campanie. Paris: Dentu, Imprimeur-libraire, 1801, via https://vulcan.lindahall.org/12_large.shtml

VOR ETWA 40.000 YR BZK FAND DIE GRÖßTE ERUPTION DES CAMPANIAN IGNIMBRITE (CI) IN DEN PHLEGRÄISCHEN FELDERN STATT.

NACHWEISE DES ASCHEREGENS DIESES SPÄTLEISTOZÄNEN VULKANISCHEN EREIGNISSES,
KÖNNEN IN GANZ MITTELEUROPA GEFUNDEN WERDEN.

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

DIESE FUNDORTE SIND IN MEHREREN PUBLIKATIONEN FESTGEHALTEN, Z.B. DURCH GENAUE KOORDINATEN ODER VERWEISE AUF STÄDTE, REGIONEN, HÖHLEN UND ARCHÄOLOGISCHE STÄTTEN.

ID 45: FRANCHTHI CAVE (GREECE)

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the Campanian Ignimbrite deposits, including archaeological and sampling sites mentioned in the paper. Solid squares: CI tephra occurrences and related thickness in cm (in italics if reworked) [modified from *Cornell et al.*, 1983; *Amirkhanov et al.*, 1993; *Cini Castagnoli et al.*, 1995; *Narcisi and Vezzoli*, 1999; *Fedele et al.*, 2002; *Upton et al.*, 2002]. Dotted area in central Italy: distribution of the CI-derived paleosol (CI-PS [Frezzotti and *Narcisi*, 1996]). Solid triangles: archaeological sites with CI ash layer. Blank triangles: archaeological sites with ash layer attributed to the CI on the basis of cultural-stratigraphic position and ^{14}C dating (*Fedele et al.*, 2002; *Giaccio and Isaia*, on file). Solid circles: selected European Palaeolithic sites within the area potentially affected by the CI air-fall.

FRANCHTHI CAVE (GREECE) IN FEDELE ET AL. (2003)

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Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_45/index.html

Squirrel Data | G PSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Franchthi Cave (Greece)

https://fuzzy-squirrel.github.io/data/cisite_45/

The Franchthi Cave (Greece) resource is powered by Static GenPubby generated using the [SRRBIOing Unicon ODS Plugin](#)

Search: format:

Description:

Property	Value
campanian (rdf:isinstanceof)	franchthi mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
centralFeature (fr:hasCentralFeature)	Ignimbrite (G)
author (rdf:type)	Hodde et al., 2003 (xsd:string)
parent (rdf:type)	Campanian Ignimbrite Project (rdf:Class) (CampanianIgnimbriteProject) (G)
url (rdf:type)	Campanian Ignimbrite Project (rdf:Class) (CampanianIgnimbriteProject) (G)
url (rdf:type)	Archaeology of the TRL Archiving at ODS (G)
url (rdf:type)	Open the Cave (G)
url (rdf:type)	ODS UK govt (xsd:string) (UK.gov) (en)
type (rdf:type)	Entity (Greece) (G)
type (rdf:type)	Archaeological Site (G)
type (rdf:type)	Archaeological Site (G)
type (rdf:type)	Geographical Related from Literature (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
label (rdf:type)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
label (rdf:type)	franchthi (xsd:string) (G)
label (rdf:type)	franchthi (xsd:string) (G)
label (rdf:type)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
label (rdf:type)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
is member (rdf:type)	Geographical Related from Literature (rdf:langstring) (Greece) (en)
is member (rdf:type)	Entity Instance Collection (Greece) (collection) (G)
is member (rdf:type)	Archaeological Site (G)
is member (rdf:type)	Entity Instance Collection (Greece) (collection) (G)
is member (rdf:type)	Archaeological Site (G)
is member (rdf:type)	Archaeological Site (G)

FRANCHTHI CAVE AS ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE IN THE LOD CLOUD

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network Nuts?

Site Instances Collection EN

http://fuzzy-squirrel.link/data/Site_collection

The Site Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<code>FeatureCollection</code> (gsp:FeatureCollection) [x]
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Site Instances Collection (rdf:langString) [iso639:en]
<code>member</code> (dfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">71 valuesAcerra Sink (fsl:dc:site_1)Acqua Fidia (fsl:dc:site_2)Baita Alba (Romania) (fsl:dc:site_57)Batajnica (fsl:dc:site_104)Bratul Borcea (Romania) (fsl:dc:site_56)Capezzano (fsl:dc:site_3)Casola (fsl:dc:site_4)Castelcivita Cave (fsl:dc:site_5)Copechia (fsl:dc:site_6)

ALL DIESE FUNDORTE UND INFOS KÖNNEN ALS LOD PUBLIZIERT WERDEN ...

Configure Own RDF Resource

Namen und RDF Ressourcen URL eingeben um eine automatische Konfiguration durchzuführen

Typ der RDF Resource:

RDF Resource Name:

RDF Ressourcen URL:

Authentifizierung

Benutzername (Optional):

Passwort (Optional):

RDF Resource permanent hinzufügen

https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```
1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType WHERE {
2 ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
3 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
4 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
5 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 }
```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (4) FeatureCollections GeometryColl

- Entity
- Place
- Site [71] [71]
 - Acerra Sink (cisite_1)
 - Acqua Fidia (cisite_2)
 - Balta Alba (Romania) (cisite_57)
 - Batajnica (cisite_104)
 - Bratul Borcea (Romania) (cisite_56)
 - Capezzano (cisite_3)
 - Casola (cisite_4)
 - Castelcivita Cave (cisite_5)
 - Copecchia (cisite_6)
 - Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (cisite_51)
 - Cuma (cisite_7)
 - Dobrogea (Romania) (cisite_53)
 - Dunaszekcsó (cisite_103)
 - Franchthi Cave (Greece) (cisite_45)
 - Golema Pesht Cave near Zdunje ...
 - Gulf of Naples (cisite_8)

... SIND ABFRAGBAR ÜBER DAS SPARQL UNICORN AUS EINEM SOLID POD ...

https://fuzzy-si.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cj_full.ttl

unicorn_sites — Objekte gesamt:104, gefiltert: 104, gewählt: 0

	id	label	ref	spatialType
1	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_1	Acerra Sink	Scandone et al., 1991	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Sink
2	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_2	Acqua Fidia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
3	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_57	Balta Alba (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
4	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_104	Batajnica	Obrecht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
5	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_104	Batajnica	Buggie, B. et al. (2013)	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
6	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_104	Batajnica	Buggie, B. et al. (2014)	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
7	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_26	Bratul Borcea (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
8	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_3	Capezzano	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
9	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_4	Casola	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
10	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_5	Castelcivita Cave	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
11	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_5	Castelcivita Cave	Giaccio et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
12	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_6	Copcechia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
13	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_51	Crvna Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
14	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_51	Crvna Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
15	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_7	Cuma	Pappalardo et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
16	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2014	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
17	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
18	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_103	Dunazekcső	Obrecht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
19	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_103	Dunazekcső	Ujvári, G. et al. (2016)	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
20	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
21	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_45	Franchthi Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
22	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowie et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
23	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_50	Golema Pesht Cave near Zdu...	Lowie et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
24	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_8	Gulf of Naples	Arienzo et al., 2009	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Bight
25	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowie et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
26	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowie et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
27	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_61	Kosijev (Serbia)	Baykal et al., 2018	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
28	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_46	Kissoura (Greece)	Lowie et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
29	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_60	Kostenki (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
30	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/data/csite_59	Kostenki-Borshchevo (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-si.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite

Alle Objekte anzeigen

... ZUR ANALYSE IN QGIS.

Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76

“In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urlaia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], **some 15 km south of the Danube River**. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities.”

Pötter et al. (2021), p.5

“The Urlaia (URL) LPS is **located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea** (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017).”

WO IST URLUIA / RUMÄNIEN?

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

URLUIA (ROMANIA) = ID:52
CA. 44.0947, 27.9021

http://fuzzy-squirrel.link/data/cisite_52

Property	Value
contains(Desc)	Redspot mentioned in a scientific paper (ref langString) (iso6391 en)
certainty(Level)	medium (fo medium) [x]
hasReference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fitzsimmons et al., 2014, 2013 (xsd string) Clarett et al., 2017 (xsd string) Pfister et al., 2023 (xsd string)
partOf (fcl partOf)	CampianiiGrinDirbuProject (fo CampianiiGrinDirbuProject) [x]
siteType	ArchaeologicalSite (fo ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType	InhabitedPlace (fo InhabitedPlace) [x]
hasCoordinates (gpr hasCoordinates)	cisite_52_geom (fo cisite_52_geom)
type (rdf type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov Entity) [x] Place (skos Place) [x] Site (fo Site) [x]
comment (rdfs comment)	CI findspot related from literature (ref langString) (iso6391 en)
label (rdfs label)	Urliua (Romania) (ref langString) (iso6391 en)
closeMatch (skos closeMatch)	664132 (gpr 664132) [x]
prefLabel (skos prefLabel)	Urliua (Romania) (ref langString) (iso6391 en)
scopeNote (skos scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (ref langString) (iso6391 en)
isMember (rdfs member of)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fo4 Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fo4 Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fo4 Site_collection)
isUsed (prov used of)	cisite_52_activity (fo4 cisite_52_activity)

CLC:code	131
CLC:explanation	See http://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Romania_CLC_Import .
CLC:shapeld	6840
CLC:year	2006
landuse	quarry
source	European Environment Agency (EEA), CORINE Land Cover, 2006
source:ro	Agenția Europeană de Mediu, CORINE Land Cover, 2006

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/84975654>

AUS BEIDEN INFORMATIONEN LÄSST SICH NÄHERUNGSWEISE
DIE FUNDORT-KOORDINATE BESTIMMEN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_52

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Nuts?

Urluia (Romania) EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_52

The Urluia (Romania) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGS Plugin

Search:

Description: comment:ci findspot related from literature

Description: scopenote:ci findspot related from literature

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc)	Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south o [...]" (rdf:langString) (xsd:string) (xsd391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Fitzsimmons et al., 2014 (xsd:string)Fitzsimmons et al., 2013 (xsd:string)Obrecht et al., 2017 (xsd:string)Pötter et al., 2021 (xsd:string)
<code>geoID</code> (fsl:geoID)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
<code>geoType</code> (fsl:geoType)	archaeologicalSite (fsl:archaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsl:spatialType)	archaeologicalSite (fsl:archaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry)	<code>cisite_52_geom</code> (fsl:cisite_52_geom)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Entity (prov:Entity) [x]Place (gsp:Place) [x]Site (fsl:Site) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (xsd391:en)
<code>label</code> (skos:label)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (xsd391:en)
<code>closeMatch</code> (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">IR127 (gsp:IR127) [x]IR1995a (gsp:IR1995a) [x]
<code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel)	Urluia (Romania) (rdf:langString) (xsd391:en)
<code>scopeNotes</code> (skos:scopeNotes)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (xsd391:en)
<code>is member of</code> (rdfs:member of)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection)Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection)Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
<code>is used</code> (prov:used of)	<code>cisite_52_activity</code> (fsl:cisite_52_activity)

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_52_geom/index.html

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc)	Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south o [...]" (rdf:langString) (xsd:string) (xsd391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
<code>asWKT</code> (gsp:asWKT)	+http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326+ POINT(27.9021 44.0947) (gsp:wktLiteral)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	Point (sf:Point) [x]
<code>Is hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry) of	Urluia (Romania) (fsl:cisite_52)
<code>Is member</code> (rdfs:member of)	Point Instances Collection (fsl:Point_collection)

URLUIA (ROMANIA) = ID:52

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

- Wikibase
- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements

- In other languages
- Add links

Item Discussion

Auel AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

[edit](#)

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Auel AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

Instance of Geological Site [edit](#)

[+ 0 references](#) [+ add reference](#) [+ add value](#)

related to <https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391> [edit](#)

related to type <http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch>

[+ 0 references](#) [+ add reference](#) [+ add value](#)

has reference Schenk et al. (2024) [edit](#)

[+ 1 reference](#) [+ add value](#)

has coordinate

50°16′57.0″N, 6°35′42.4″E

[has certainty level](#)

High

[certainty description](#)

stated in scientific paper

[method used](#)

Georeferencing

[acting person](#)

Fiona Schenk

[method description](#)

site survey

[has source subtype](#)

Paper

[has source](#)

Textual Description

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

... GEHT AUCH IN EINER WIKIBASE: AUEL AU3 [Q70]

RESEARCH & FAIRIFICATION TOOLS

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SQUIRREL PAPERS

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AUF DER WORKING PAPERS, DATEN, SOFTWARE ...

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Volume 6

Overview

- Issue 1
- Issue 2: *Special Issue on data and software*
- Issue 3: *Special Issue on conferences and talks*
- Issue 4: *Special Issue on NFDI related topics*
- Issue 5: *Special Issue on the UK-Ireland DH Association Annual Event 2024 at UCC*

Issue 2

Special Issue on data and software

#1 [Software] SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

- Authors: F. Thiery; T. Homburg
- Version: 0.17
- Repository: [sparqlunicornGoesGIS](#)
- Release: @v0.17
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10779466](#)

#2 [Software] SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

- Authors: T. Homburg; F. Thiery
- Version: 0.17
- Repository: [sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc](#)
- Release: @v0.17
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10780476](#)

#3 [Software] TiGeR - Time Geospatial RDF

- Authors: F. Thiery - A.W. Mees
- Version: 1.0
- Repository: [tiger](#)
- Release: @v1.0
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11064284](#)

#4 [Software] alligator - Allen Transformer

- Authors: F. Thiery - A.W. Mees
- Version: 1.1
- Repository: [alligator](#)
- Release: @v1.1
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11064526](#)

#5 [Software] SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

- Authors: F. Thiery; T. Homburg
- Version: 0.17.1
- Repository: [sparqlunicornGoesGIS](#)
- Release: @v0.17.1
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13828632](#)

Issue 3

Special Issue on conferences and talks

#1 [Presentation] 3D and Research Data Management (RDM): Examples for semantic 3D annotation/modelling in the data qualification process in the NFDI consortia NFDI4Objects (N4O) and NFDI4Culture (N4C)

- Authors: F. Thiery; L. Rossenova; Z. Schubert
- Event: Oldenburger 3D-Tage (31. January - 01. February 2024)
- Session: Kulturerbe
- Location: Jade-Hochschule, Oldenburg
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10580308](#)

#2 [Presentation] Research Software Engineering in NFDI4Objects: Community building, implementation of FAIRification Tools and scripting in Computational Archaeology

- Authors: F. Thiery; L. Schubert; F. Fricke
- Event: deRSE2024 (05. - 07. March 2024)
- Session: RSE in Digital Humanities
- Location: Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10774878](#)

#3 [Poster] FOSS N4O Management Hub: Using RSE skills and Open Source Software to propose a heterogenous Management Hub in NFDI4Objects

- Authors: F. Thiery; F. Fricke
- Event: deRSE2024 (05. - 07. March 2024)
- Session: Poster Session
- Location: Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10756823](#)

#4 [Poster] Research Software Engineering within the NFDI (INFRA-WG-RSE)

- Authors: B. Flemisch; F. Thiery
- Event: deRSE2024 (05. - 07. March 2024)
- Session: Poster Session
- Location: Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10805071](#)

#5 [Presentation] The SPARQL Unicorn: A Research Tool for Linked Open Data in QGIS and git-action-based ontology documentation

- Authors: F. Thiery; T. Homburg
- Event: deRSE2024 (05. - 07. March 2024)
- Session: RSE in Digital Humanities
- Location: Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg
- DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10790939](#)

BEISPIELE AUS VOLUME 6 (2024)

LINKED OPEN DATA PROJEKTE

LOD PROJEKTE
LINKED OPEN OGHAM

OGHAM!

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. JHD.N.CHR.
EARLY MEDIEVAL
"PRIMITIVE IRISH"

VERBREITUNG
IRLAND
(+ WALES, ENGLAND, ISLE OF MAN)

A	M	H	B
O	G	D	L
U	NG	T	V
E	Z	C	S
I	R	Q	N

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THE OPEN OGHAM DATA WORKFLOW!

- Project page
- Discussion
- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate
- Leicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme
- Tools
- What links here
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- Page information
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

In Wikipedia [Add links](#)

Project page Discussion

Read Edit View history More Search Wikidata

Wikidata:WikiProject OghamStones

- Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject OghamStones](#) (Q129491028) supported by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network (Q73601970)
- Commons Category: [Category:Ogham stones](#)

Contents [hide]

- 1 Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition
- 2 Examples
 - 2.1 Ogham Stones in the Cork Public Museum
 - 2.2 Ogham Stones at the UCC Stone Corridor
 - 2.3 Ogham Stones at Trinity College, Dublin
 - 2.4 Ogham Stones at the National Museum, Dublin
 - 2.5 Ogham Stones at Músaem Chorca Dhuibhne
- 3 Statements to model an Ogham Stone in the wild
- 4 Examples
 - 4.1 Ogham Stones in the Co. Kerry
 - 4.2 TODO
- 5 Contributors

Statements to model an Ogham Stone in an exhibition [edit]

Property	Example	description
Statements		
instance of (P31)	ogham stone (Q2010147) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q105602843) archaeological artifact (Q220556)	defines it as an Ogham Stone, archaeological artefact and Ogham Stone Semantic Concept
part of (P381)	WikiProject OghamStones (Q129491028) Ogham Stone Semantic Concept (Q105602843)	part of WikiProjects and a semantic concept
image (P18)	divers	Wikimedia Commons image. If multiple add pref. rank (optional)
country (P17)	divers	country, e.g. Republic of Ireland (Q27)
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	divers	county, e.g. County Cork (Q152475)
location (P276)	divers	museum + exhibition, e.g. University College Cork (Q1574155) + UCC Stone Corridor (Q121562049)
coordinate location (P625)	WGS84	using qualifier location (P276) ex situ (Q1383330), sourcing circumstances (P1485) on-site survey (Q120965426), determination method (P456) on-site survey (Q120965426), subject has role (P2868) exhibition (Q454660), stated in (P248) OpenStreetMap (Q268), reference OpenStreetMap
creator (P170)	Ogham Person Concept (Q111087321)	Ogham Person as creator (only needed if non-free artwork image URL (P8000) is used)
collection (P196)	divers	collection, e.g. Stone Corridor University College Cork (Q26379477)
inventory number (P217)	divers	inventory number of the collection, set a pref. rank
location of discovery (P138)	divers	ogham site, e.g. Barrahaunin (Ogham Site) (Q50378412)
external data available at URL (P1325)	LURL	ref. to 3D-model in Sketchfab, using qualifier object has role (P3831) 3D model (Q3859833), publisher (P123), published in (P1433), copyright license (P275), add pref. rank
inscription (P1854)	latin	inscription, e.g. C[AR]RITACC MMAQI MOU CAGG (Latin)
state of conservation (P5815)	divers	status, e.g. partially destroyed (Q26539150) (optional)
non-free artwork image URL (P8000)	divers	external image (optional), using qualifier copyright license (P276), publisher (P123), object has role (P3831)
partially coincident with (P1382)	divers	other concepts, e.g. BARHA1 (Ogham Stone Concept by CISP) (Q109675166), CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (Q26377650)
Identifiers		
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11563)	divers	Open Street Map Node

DAS WIKIDATA WIKI PROJECT OGHAM STONES

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/GSD3000003>

The Munster resource is powered by [Static GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q131438 (wde:Q131438) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	GSD3000003_geom (fsld:GSD3000003_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Feature (gsp:Feature) [x]• Province (oghamonto:Province) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	Munster (rdfs:langString) (iso639:ten)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Feature Instances Collection (fsld:Feature_collection)• Province Instances Collection (fsld:Province_collection)

OGHAM STONES IN THE PROVINCE MUNSTER

OGHAM STONES IN THE PROVINCE MUNSTER

CIIC 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)^{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y10000303>

The CIIC 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format:

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	0540000120 (fslid:0540000120)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	069385424 (wde:069385424) [x]
shows (oghamonto:shows)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">OW6 (fslid:OW6)OW8 (fslid:OW8)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [x]OghamStone_CIIC (oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC) [x]Resource (ldp:Resource) [x]Resource (Resource) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (rdflangString) (iso6391:en)
label (rdfs:label)	CIIC 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister) (rdflangString) (iso6391:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	81 (xsd:string)
creator (terms:creator)	0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]
license (terms:license)	deed.de (deed.de) [x]
rightsHolder (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]0000-0003-4696-2101 (0000-0003-4696-2101) [x]
inDataset (void:inDataset)	Linked_Open_Ogham (fslid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [1367 oghamonto:shows]
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStonesCIIC (fslid:PythonStonesCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones.csv (og_stones.csv) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	Y10000303_activity (fslid:Y10000303_activity)

OGHAM STONES IN THE PROVINCE MUNSTER

CIIC 81

- UCC CORK STONE CORRIDOR: #4
- OSM: NODE/11071361392
- WIKIDATA: Q106680733

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthierygeo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A]O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/562702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheeragh Ringfort

RATH CALLED
LISHEENAGREINE
CA. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery,
CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

GEOREFERENZIERUNG DES FUNDORTS MIT HILFE VON OPEN STREET MAP

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	Q106680733 ogham stone edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

via <https://www.istor.org/stable/25505959>

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

- determination method [georeferencing](#)
- object has role [book entry \(Ogham\)](#)
- subject has role [archaeological site](#)
- statement in [academic journal article](#)

[1 reference](#)

- reference URL <https://www.corkhist.ie/wp-content/uploads/jfiles/1931/b1931-020.pdf>
- <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

CIIC 81 IN WIKIDATA → FOUND IN GARRANES (LISHEENAGREINE)

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

HEUTIGER STANDORT IM UCC STONE CORRIDOR

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)
 Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	<div>Q106680733 ogham stone edit</div> <div>0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div>
	<div>Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept edit</div> <div>0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div>
	<div>Q106680733 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project) edit</div> <div>0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

51°53'37.7254"N, 8°29'31.6313"W

- location [ex situ](#)
- sourcing circumstances [on-site survey](#)
- determination method [on-site survey](#)
- subject has role [exhibition](#)
- stated in [OpenStreetMap](#)

[1 reference](#)

[OpenStreetMap node ID](#) [11071361392](#)

CIIC 81 IN WIKIDATA → CURRENTLY AT UCC CORK #4

LOD PROJEKTE

HOLY WELLS

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
- Revised changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

In Wikipedia [Add links](#)

Project page Discussion

Read Edit View history More Search Wikidata

Wikidata:WikiProject HolyWells

Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject HolyWells](#) (Q125443454) supported by the [Research Squirrel Engineers Network](#) (Q73901970)

Contents [hide]

- 1 Holy Wells in Ireland
- 1.1 Statements to model a holy well in Ireland
- 1.2 Examples
- 1.3 SPARQL created List
- 1.4 SPARQL List as Map / Image Map
- 1.5 Contributors

Holy Wells in Ireland [edit]

Statements to model a holy well in Ireland [edit]

Use English and Irish labels in the header, where known.

Property	Example	Explanation
instance of (P31)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q125443332)	always use this: defines it as a holy well, no matter whether there is still veneration happening or not.
	holy well (Q1371047)	
instance of (P31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • state of use (P5617): "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case • state of conservation (P5816): preserved (Q26557561)/ in danger (Q26555026)/ demolished or destroyed (Q26555015) 	
instance of (P31)	religious site (Q10589886)	only where veneration is still happening, i.e. annual patterns or people regularly visiting the well for private prayers or to retrieve the holy water
instance of (P31)	water source (Q10713454)	only where there is actually still water at the site, helps to filter out dried up wells/ springs
country (P17)	Republic of Ireland (Q27)	---
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q180231) + Balleen (Q50553357)	County + civil parish
diocese (P758)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q873907)	Roman Catholic diocese in which the holy well is located
coordinate location (P825)		coordinate location derived from OpenStreetMap or Historic Environment Viewer add reference URL (P254) or stated in (P248)
street address (P3875)		use, when the only location given is a field name or similar
described by source (P1343)	O'Kelly: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q12837401) Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (Q120466144) The Schoote' Collection (Q126303246) Canon W. Carrigan: The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q125454042) with its volumes	add page(s) (P304) or reference URL (P54)
image (P18)		image
video (P15)		
Commons category (P373)	Category:Toberbride, Callan [?]	
named after (P116)	Bright of Kildare (Q88076) eye (Q7354)	saint representing patron saint or body part representing cure for ailment
open days (P3025)		pattern day(s), if it is still celebrated
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4057)	KK008-133---	plus reference URL (P54)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11902)	6153432366	OpenStreetMap Node ID or way ID
Wiki Loves Monuments ID (P2186)	IE-KK-0327	WikiLovesMonuments ID (optional for accessible ones)

DAS WIKIDATA WIKI PROJECT HOLY WELLS

HOLY WELLS IN WIKIDATA VIA [HTTPS://W.WIKI/AQ2F](https://w.wiki/AQ2F)

HOLY WELLS IN WIKIDATA VIA [HTTPS://W.WIKI/AQ2F](https://w.wiki/AQ2F)

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Wikidata

Toberlachtain (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny

Total Lachtain (St. Lachtain's Well) - Toberlachtain

+ 12 more languages

Language	Label	Description	Short name
English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	
Arabic	No label defined	No description defined	

All external languages

Statements

instance of

- holy well
- Holy Well Semantic Concept
- spring

holy well

area of use: abandoned
year to line: 1855

Image

File:Toberlachtain Well Lactain 01.jpg
3,000 × 2,000 (5.54 MB)

named after

- Lachtain mac Tairn

country

- Ireland

located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny
- Freshford

disease

- Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory

coordinate location

collection

- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny II

inventory number

- 137

medical condition treated

- conjunctivitis
- eye infection

external data available at URL

- https://www70760.com/35-moodyfreshford-st-lachtain-well-2019-06-16/176124742330770427704870/

described by source

- Clarys, The Place-Names of County Kilkenny
- Historic Environment Viewer (OSparis)
- The Schoolyard Collection
- Letters containing information relative to the antiquities of the County of Kilkenny, collected during the progress of the Ordnance Survey in 1838
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory II

described by source

- 6 Inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny in terms of documentary coverage, location, ritual practice and onomastic context, vol. I
- Patrick O'Donoghue, The holy wells of County Kilkenny II
- Notes and Comments of County Kilkenny by Paris Anderson
- Blairner Cartmel, Thracianites
- Historical, Social and Political Sketches of Freshford
- Red Book of Ossory

Commons category

- Toberlachtain

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

- KK013-025----

OpenStreetMap node ID

- 30503837

Wiki Loves Monuments ID

- IR-KK-0248

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK013-025----

1 reference

OpenStreetMap way ID

30503837

0 references

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL IN WIKIDATA

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)

Version #7
added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #152597977

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subcircular water basin which is covered in water lentils.
name	Toberlachtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:etymology:wiki	Q18674069
name:ga	Tobar Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:ESmr	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

© OpenStreetMap Mitwirkende | Spenden, Website und API-Bedingungen

FRESHFORD: ST LACHTAIN'S WELL IN OSM

KILLAMERY: ST NICHOLAS'S WELL

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126458702>

Wikidata

St. Nicholas's Well (Q126458702)

holy well in Kilkenny, Co. Kilkenny
St. Nicholas's Well (en) St. Nicholas's Well (de) St. Nicholas's Well (en)

Language **Label** **Description** **Also known as**

English	St. Nicholas's Well	holy well in Kilkenny, Co. Kilkenny	St. Nicholas's Well (en)
German	No label defined	No description defined	St. Nicholas's Well (de)
ISO 639-3	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

Instance of

- holy well
- holy well in Kilkenny, Co. Kilkenny

Holy Well Semantic Context

- holy well

Image

Named after

- Saint Nicholas

country

- Ireland

Included in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny
- Kilkenny
- Kilkenny

diocese

- Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory

coordinate location

location

- Patrick O'Donoghue: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II

inventory number

- 115

external data available at URL

- Map: https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/126458702

described by source

- Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland)
- O'Kelly: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny
- The Schooner Collection
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory IV
- 25 inch mapping series (Ireland)
- 6 inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- 6 inch Last Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- Patrick O'Donoghue: The holy wells of County Kilkenny in terms of documentary coverage, location, ritual practice and onomastics context, vol. I

- The Schooner Collection
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory IV
- 25 inch mapping series (Ireland)
- 6 inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- 6 inch Last Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland
- Patrick O'Donoghue: The holy wells of County Kilkenny in terms of documentary coverage, location, ritual practice and onomastics context, vol. I
- Patrick O'Donoghue: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II
- Letters containing information relative to the antiquities of the county of Kilkenny collected during the progress of the Ordnance Survey (n. 1839)

Commons category

- Saint Nicholas's Well, Kilkenny

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

OpenStreetMap node ID

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK030-008007-

▶ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID

616796637

▼ 0 references

KILLAMERY: ST NICHOLAS'S WELL IN WIKIDATA

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/6167966637>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen

Knoten: Saint Nicholas's Well (6167966637)

Version #13

added wikidata to #holy well

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling
Änderungssatz #152518873
Standort: 52.4752746, -7.4459883

Tags

denomination	roman_catholic
description	Stone lined water basin of c.1m width with a large carved stone marking the spot. Water is covered in water lentils.
drinking_water	no
man_made	water_well
mapillary	759508952563297
name	Saint Nicholas's Well
name:en	Saint Nicholas's Well
name:etymology:wiki data	Q44269
name:ga	Tobar San Niclais
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
pump	no
ref:ESmr	KK030-008007
religion	christian
	O'Kelly: Placenames.

© OpenStreetMap Mitwirkende Spenden, Website und API-Bedingungen

KILLAMERY: ST NICHOLAS'S WELL IN OSM

LOD PROJEKTE
ROCK ART IN ALTA

ALTA MUSEUM
Help CONTACT US

Alta	
Hjemmeluft	
Apana Gärd	velg feltnr ▼
Apanes	velg feltnr ▼
Bergbukten	velg feltnr ▼
Bergheim	velg feltnr ▼
Decca	velg feltnr ▼
MBA	velg feltnr ▼
Ole Pedersen	velg feltnr ▼
Amtmannsnes	velg feltnr ▼
Isnestoften	velg feltnr ▼
Kongshus	velg feltnr ▼
Kråknes	velg feltnr ▼
Kårfjord	velg del ▼
Storsteinen	velg feltnr ▼
Svarstkog	velg feltnr ▼
Toilevik	velg feltnr ▼
Transfarelv	velg feltnr ▼
Åreya	velg feltnr ▼

Søk i arkivet

ALTA MUSEUM
Help CONTACT US

1. Nasjonalbibliotek > [Romsdal og Dovre](#) > [Hjemmeluft](#) > [Decca](#) > [Bergbukten](#) > [Alta](#) > [Alta](#)

Sortieren nach zuletzt modifert +

Stor og Prenter

Filter

Figurer

- Ann
- Bear
- Bear den
- Bear track
- Bird
- Boat
- Bow
- Dog/wolf
- Drum
- Elk
- Elk head stuff
- Elk track
- Fish
- Fishing box
- Hogg/Prenter

Map source: © Kartverket

Das Bild ist möglicherweise urheberrechtlich geschützt. 2 km Nutzungsbedingungen

DAS OPEN ALTAROCKART.NO FOTOWEB ARCHIV

ORTHOFOTOS DER ROCK ART ELEMENTE

UMZEICHNUNG UND ANSPRACHE DER ROCK ART FEATURES

**ALTA
MUSEUM**

World Heritage
Rock Art Centre

link to existing
information in
altarockart.no

extract information on rock
art paintings:
location, depictions

altarockart.no

input into Wikidata,
link to existing
datasets in wikidata

extract enriched
data with the help
of the **SPARQL
Unicorn**

further analysis
with open source
software

DER LINKED REINDEERS WORKFLOW

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate
- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code
- In Wikipedia
- [Add links](#)

Wikidata:WikiProject LinkedReindeersAlta

- Wikidata Entry: [WikiProject LinkedReindeersAlta](#) (Q13044202) supported by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network (Q7390107)
- Commons Category: [Category:Rock Art of Alta](#)

Contents [hide]

- Statements to model Rock Art Figures
- Examples
 - Wikidata Query
 - Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1
 - Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 4B
- Contributors

Statements to model Rock Art Figures [edit]

Property	Example	description
instance of (P31)	rock art (Q1211146) petroglyph (Q42195) carving (Q13039303) archaeological artifact (Q220059)	defines it as an rock art feature
part of (P381)	Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (Q2395456) Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 4B (Q13044194)	part of specific Alta Rock Art area
coordinate location (P625)	WGS84	
creator (P170)	unknown value	qualifier: object of statement has role (P3831) anonymous (Q4233716)
depicts (P180)	divers	one as preferred rank using qualifier: object of statement has role (P3831) e.g. spear (Q44475), hunting (Q35993)
collection (P195)	Rock Art of Alta Collection (Q82888025)	
non-free artwork image URL (P8500)	divers	link to Alta Rock Art Foto Archive

Examples [edit]

Wikidata Query [edit]

- <https://w.wiki/BSaj>

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_LinkedReindeersAlta#Wikidata_Query

Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 [edit]

- Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-85) (Q100149218)
- Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (E-126) (Q130441488)
- Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (G-169) (Q82888499)

WIKIDATA PROJECT: LINKED REINDEERS IN ALTA

via <https://wiki/BSai>

Wikidata Query Service

Beispiele Hilfe Weitere Werkzeuge Abfragegenerator

```
1 SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?preferredDepictionLabel ?depictionRoleLabel ?geo ?image ?match WHERE {
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q220659.
3   ?item wdt:P195 wd:Q82688025.
4   ?item wdt:P180 ?preferredDepiction.
5   ?item rdfs:label ?label.
6   OPTIONAL { ?item p:P180 ?s1. ?s1 pq:P3831 ?depictionRole. }
7   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
8   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P6500 ?image. }
9   OPTIONAL {?item wdt:P973 ?match . }
10  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
11 }
12 ORDER BY (?preferredDepictionLabel)
```

SPARQL ABFRAGE IN WIKIDATA

item	itemLabel	preferredDepictionLabel	depictionRoleLabel	geo	image	match
Q:13044222	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (E-139)	bear	pregnancy	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju338.jpg info>	
Q:130442249	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (E-140)	bear	baby animal	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju337.jpg info>	
Q:130443249	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (D-127)	bird	hunting	Point(23 19403955 69 9515757)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20131210mahy003.JPG info>	
Q:130443269	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-7)	bird	goose	Point(23 19403955 69 951575694)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20131210mahy007.JPG info>	
Q:082689469	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (G-169)	boat	hunting	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/aaa20120321laju308.jpg info>	<https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>
Q:082690112	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (D-195)	boat	water transport	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju268.jpg info>	<https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>
Q:130442150	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-148)	boat	hunting	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120704laju010.JPG info>	
Q:130442514	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-157)	boat	fishing	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120704laju107.JPG info>	
Q:130442551	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-145)	boat	hunting	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120712laju015.JPG info>	
Q:130442575	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-147)	boat	fishing	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120629laju008.JPG info>	
Q:130443350	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-34/35)	boat	hunting	Point(23 194039555 69 951575694)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20141119maar010.JPG info>	
Q:130443365	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-30/31)	boat	fishing	Point(23 194039555 69 951575694)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20141119maar011.JPG info>	
Q:130443448	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-53)	boat	crew	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	<https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>
Q:130443464	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-54)	boat	crew	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju089.JPG info>	<https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>
Q:130443479	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (E-177)	boat	crew	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju295.jpg info>	<https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>
Q:100149218	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-85)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5002-Fotoarkivet/Folder%20118/20100727laju214.JPG info>	
Q:100151497	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-83)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5002-Fotoarkivet/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130441656	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (E-148)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130442085	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (A-150)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177546111 69 949131111)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130442326	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-35)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130442429	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-48)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130442471	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-45)	domesticated reindeer	antlers	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130441488	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (E-126)	human	Bow	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130442389	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-43)	human	spear	Point(23 177886944 69 948933055)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju090.JPG info>	
Q:130443410	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 2 (7)	human	hunting	Point(23 178323938 69 94908333)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20110727laju214.JPG info>	
Q:130443313	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-23)	moose	pregnancy	Point(23 194039555 69 951575694)	<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20131210mahy003.JPG info>	

via <https://w.wiki/BSai>

SPARQL ERGEBNIS IN WIKIDATA

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AUSSCHNITT AUS HJEMMELUFT, BERGBUKTEN I, ABSCHNITT C

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
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- Page information
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Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-48) (Q130442429)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-48) [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-48)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-48)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of	rock art	0 references
	petroglyph	0 references
	carving	0 references
	archaeological artifact	0 references

Rentier

depicts

[domesticated reindeer](#)
 object of statement has role [antlers](#)
[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[antlers](#)
[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

collection

[Rock Art of Alta Collection](#)
[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

non-free artwork image URL

<https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%201116/20120321laju096.JPG.info>
[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Q130442429

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
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Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-45) (Q130442471)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-45) [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)
[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-45)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-45)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	rock art edit	0 references +
	petroglyph edit	0 references +
	carving edit	0 references +
	archaeological artifact edit	0 references +

Rentier

depicts

[domesticated reindeer](#) [edit](#)

object of statement has role [antlers](#)
[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[antlers](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

collection

[Rock Art of Alta Collection](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

non-free artwork image URL

[https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju102.JPG.info](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[edit](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Q130442471

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-43) (Q130442389)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-43) [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-43)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-43)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

Instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rock art edit 0 references +
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> petroglyph edit 0 references +
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> carving edit 0 references +
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> archaeological artifact edit 0 references +

Mensch

depicts

- human
 - object of statement has role **spear**
 - 0 references
- spear
 - 0 references

collection

- Rock Art of Alta Collection [edit](#)
- 0 references [+](#)
- [add reference](#)
- [add value](#)

non-free artwork image URL

- <https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321laju106.JPG.info> [edit](#)
- 0 references [+](#)
- [add reference](#)
- [add value](#)

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Q130442389

Karin Tansem, VAM World Heritage Rock Art Centre - Alta Museum CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 (2015)

AUSSCHNITT AUS HJEMMELUFT, OLE PEDERSEN IIA, ABSCHNITT A

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-30/31) (Q130443365)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A30/31) [edit](#)

▼ In more languages

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-30/31)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A30/31)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	 rock art edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 carving	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 archaeological artifact	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 petroglyph	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value

Boot

facts	 boat edit
	object of statement has role fishing + add reference
 human	▼ 0 references + add reference
	 crew + add value
 fish	▼ 0 references + add reference
	 fishing rod edit
	+ add reference
	+ add value
action	 Rock Art of Alta Collection edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value
-free artwork image URL	 https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20141119maar011.JPG.info edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value

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Q130443365

Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-34/35) (Q130443350)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A34/35) [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Ole Pedersen 11A (A-34/35)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Ole Pedersen 11A (A34/35)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of	rock art edit
	0 references + add reference
carving	edit
	0 references + add reference
archaeological artifact	edit
	0 references + add reference
petroglyph	edit
	0 references + add reference
+ add value	

Boat

depicts

boat [edit](#)

object of statement has role hunting

0 references

human

0 references

domesticated reindeer

0 references

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collection

Rock Art of Alta Collection [edit](#)

0 references

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

non-free artwork image URL

https://atamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20141119maar010.JPG.info [edit](#)

0 references

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Q130443350

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AUSSCHNITT AUS HJEMMELUFT, BERGBUKTEN 4B, ABSCHNITT C

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-148) (Q130442150)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 4B (C-148)

▼ In more languages

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 4B (C-148)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 4B (C-148)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	 rock art edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 petroglyph	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 carving	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
 archaeological artifact	edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
+ add value	

Boot

depicts

 boat edit
object of statement has role hunting
▼ 0 references + add reference
 human edit
▼ 0 references + add value
 crew edit
▼ 0 references + add reference
 bow edit
▼ 0 references + add value

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collection	 Rock Art of Alta Collection edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
+ add value	
non-free artwork image URL	 https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120704laju010.JPG.info edit
	▼ 0 references + add reference
+ add value	

Q130442150

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AUSSCHNITT AUS HJEMMELUFT, BERGBUKTEN I

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-53) (Q130443448)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-53)

▾ [In more languages](#)
[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-53)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-53)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of	rock art edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add reference
	carving edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add reference
	archaeological artifact edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add reference
	petroglyph edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add value

Boot

depicts	boat edit	+ add reference
	object of statement has role crew	+ add value
	▾ 0 references	
	human edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	
	crew edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	
collection	Rock Art of Alta Collection edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add value
described at URL	https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001 edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add value
non-free artwork image URL	https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/20120321iaju090.JPG.info edit	+ add reference
	▾ 0 references	+ add value

Q130443448

Item [Discussion](#)

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-54) (Q130443464)

Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-54)

▼ In more languages

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-54)	Alta Rock Art, Hjemmeluft, Bergbukten 1 (C-54)	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rock art edit ▼ 0 references + add reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> carving edit ▼ 0 references + add reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> archaeological artifact edit ▼ 0 references + add reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> petroglyph edit ▼ 0 references + add reference
	+ add value

Boot

depicts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> boat edit object of statement has role crew ▼ 0 references
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> human edit ▼ 0 references
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> crew edit ▼ 0 references
collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rock Art of Alta Collection edit ▼ 0 references + add reference + add value
described at URL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001 edit ▼ 0 references + add reference + add value
non-free artwork image URL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://altamuseum.fotoware.cloud/fotoweb/archives/5003-Photoarchive/Folder%20118/201203211aju089.JPG.info edit ▼ 0 references + add reference + add value

Q130443464

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (ID: 400001)

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Object Data

Rock Art	object type
Bedrock, Sandstone	material
Carving	technique
Helskog Period II (4800-4000), Gjerde Phase 1 (5200-4200)	culture
coming soon	country / location / POI
0m, 0m, 0m	height / width / length
coming soon	depository
coming soon	archive
1972, sections A-I	discovery
not available	person
not available	place of origin

VERKNÜPFUNG ZU FACHDATENBANKEN WIE NAVISONE

Feature 2 - Metadata

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-54)

description

400005

true

false

Images

via <https://www2.leiza.de/navis/object.html?id=400001>

Feature 1 - Metadata

Hjemmeluft: Bergbukten 1 (C-53)

description

400004

Feature ID

true

crew on feature

false

cargo on feature

Images

VERKNÜPFUNG ZU FACHDATENBANKEN WIE NAVISONE

CONCLUSION

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NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

DIE COMMUNITY KANN DABEI HELFEN RESEARCH DATA UND RESEARCH TOOLS ZU ENTWICKELN UND ZU MAINTAINEN UM AUCH SO TEIL VON NFDI ZU WERDEN :-)

FINIS!

QUESTIONS?

Florian Thiery, mail@fthiery.de, ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531